

‘Our Love, Our Control’ Programme on Sexual Health Literacy (SHL) and Behaviors in Preventing Unintended Pregnancy and Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs), during 12 February 2021 – 25 June 2021

Week/ Intervention	Concept/ Theory	Method	Activities via Facebook application
<p>Week 1 -Informed consent</p> <p>- Pre-test*</p>		<p>-Self-assessment via google questionnaire form and join the closed Facebook group</p>	<p>-The researcher informed the participants of the objectives, procedure, time period, and benefits of this research in a classroom. Each participant brought information sheet and consent form back home. The parents and participants signed an informed consent form of this research if they had mutual agreement to participate.</p> <p>-The closed Facebook group was set up by researcher team, then willing participants were invited into this group. Then they received QR code for the pre-test. A researcher checked the data.</p>

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<p>Week 2</p> <p>- ‘Clear by doctor’</p>	<p>-Health literacy: accessibility of sexual health information and services</p> <p>-Self-efficacy: Mastery experience</p>	<p>-Group discussion/ game playing</p>	<p>Objective: To increase health literacy level of accessibility of sexual health information and services.</p> <p>-Researcher provided infographic story ‘Clear by doctor’ of how to access sexual health information and services.</p> <p>-Participants was paired and then they were assigned to access sexual health information and services from any sources. Each pair looked for the most reliable sources and uploaded URL (Universal Resource Locator, URL) in the Facebook.</p> <p>-RAs (Research assistances) checked each URL and gave score for each pair. The pair who got the highest score won this game and got reward.</p> <div data-bbox="981 884 1211 1187" style="text-align: center;"> <p>The infographic is titled 'คุณหมอช่วยออกสิทธิ์' (Doctor helps you get rights) and features a cartoon doctor character. It contains Thai text providing information about sexual health services, including a list of services and a Facebook link for more information.</p> </div>

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Week 3 -‘Sex must know’	Health literacy: sufficient understanding of sexual health and services for practice	- Self-online learning/ game playing	Objective: To increase health literacy level of understanding of sexual health. -Participants watched VDO (Visual Data Object, VDO) about body and reproductive system development -Each participants was assigned to draw his/her picture of body and reproductive system change on A4 paper. Then they sent directly to RAs via LINE application. -RAs checked each URL and gave score for each pair. The pair who got the highest score won this game and got reward.
Week 4 -‘Help!!! I am not ready’	-Health literacy: 1) sufficient understanding of sexual health and services for practice, 2) decision making of sexual practice -Self-efficacy: Vicarious experience and emotional arousal	- Self-online learning/ pair discussion/ game playing	Objective: 1) To increase awareness of sexual health risk and sexual health. prevention 2) To increase health literacy level of understanding, decision making, accessibility of sexual health and services for practice. -Participants watched VDO about unwanted pregnancy and sexual transmitted diseases (STDs) experiences. -Each pair was assigned to share their experiences and discuss about how to do if they get unwanted pregnancy and STDs. 1) Who will be the first to known about this? Why? 2) How will I tell them? The answer of each pair was sent into open chat under the VDO of the closed Facebook group. -RAs checked each answer and gave score for each pair. The pair who got the highest score won this game and got reward.

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Week 5 -‘Condom matter’	Health literacy: sufficient understanding of sexual health	- Self-online learning/ pair discussion/ game playing	<p>Objective: To increase understanding of condom use.</p> <p>-Participants watched VDO about knowledge and practice of condom using.</p> <p>-Each pair was assigned to share their experiences and discuss about condom using.</p> <p>Then the impressive experiences were used to create awesome quotes of how to convinces another pair or their friends to use condom for safe sex properly. Each quote was sent to closed Facebook.</p> <p>-RAs checked each quote and gave score for each pair. The pair who got the highest score won this game and got reward.</p>

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Week 6 -‘Believable’	Health literacy: sexual health assessment	- Self-online learning/ game playing	<p>Objective: To increase level of health literacy: sexual health assessment.</p> <p>-Participants watched VDO how to analyse and assess the validity and reliability of unwanted pregnancy and STDs data.</p> <p>-Participants play Q&A game about unwanted pregnancy and STDs via ‘Kahoot’ application.</p> <p>-RAs checked the scores of each participant. The participant who got the highest score won this game and got reward.</p>

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Week 7 -‘My value’	Health literacy: decision making of sexual practice, Self-efficacy: Verbal persuasion	-Group discussion/ game playing	Objective: 1) To increase health literacy: decision making of sexual practice. 2) To increase verbal persuasion. -Participants watched VDO about how to say no/ avoid from sexual health risk situation by using rationales all analyzed pros and cons including impacts, and how to verbal persuade to the others to say no/ avoid sexual health risk situation. - Participants was assigned to answer how to say no/ to avoid if ‘Their boy/girlfriend invite he/she to hangout/ watch porn movies together without another person’. The answer of each participant was sent into open chat under the VDO of the closed Facebook group. -RAs checked the scores of each participants. The participant who got the highest score won this game and got 200 baht.

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<p>Week 8 -‘My choice’</p> <p>-Immediate assessment*</p>	<p>Health literacy: decision making of sexual practice, Self-efficacy: Verbal persuasion</p>	<p>-Group discussion/ group assignment/ game playing</p> <p>-Self-assessment via google questionnaire form</p>	<p>Objective: To increase health literacy: decision making of sexual practice. 2) To increase self-efficacy: verbal persuasion.</p> <p>-Participants were assigned to discuss among group members about their goal and plan of practices to preventing unintended pregnancy and STDs. Then each group wrote essay or poem to persuade the others to practices for preventing unintended pregnancy and STDs. The essay/ poem of each group was post in the closed Facebook group under the assignment.</p> <p>-RAs read and gave the scores of each group. The group who got the highest score won this game and got reward.</p>

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Week 9-19 -Practice in the real world	Booster weekly	- Self-online learning/ self-practice	Objective: To increase health literacy and self-efficacy. -RAs sent VDO clip weekly Week 9 watched the similar infographic story of week 2 ‘Clear by doctor’ (without assignment) Week 10 watched the similar VDO Clip of week 3 ‘Sex must know’(without assignment) Week 11 watched the similar VDO Clip of week 4 ‘Help!!! I am not ready’(without assignment) Week 12 watched the similar VDO Clip of week 5 ‘Condom matter’ (without assignment)

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Week 9-19 -Practice in the real world	Booster weekly	- Self-online learning/ self-practice	<p>Objective: To increase health literacy and self-efficacy.</p> <p>Week 13 watched the similar VDO Clip of week 6 ‘Belivable’ (without assignment)</p> <p>Week 14 watched the similar VDO Clip of week 7 ‘My value’ (without assignment)</p> <p>Week 15 watched the similar infographic story of week 2 ‘Clear by doctor’ (without assignment)</p> <p>Week 16 watched the similar VDO Clip of week 3 ‘Sex must know’(without assignment)</p>

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Week 9-19 -Practice in the real world	Booster weekly	-Self-online learning/ self-practice	Objective: To increase health literacy and self-efficacy. -RAs sent VDO clip weekly Week 17 watched the similar VDO Clip of week 4 ‘Help!!! I am not ready’ and watched the similar VDO Clip of week 5 ‘Condom matter’ (without assignment) Week 18 watched the similar VDO Clip of week 6 ‘Belivable’ (without assignment) **Week 19 watched the similar VDO Clip of week 7 ‘My value’ (without assignment)
Week 20 -Post-test*		-Self-assessment via google questionnaire form	-No other activity

*Comparison group did only the pre-test, immediate assessment, and post-test via google form as well as intervention group.